

Information Integration on Web-based Applications and Services J.UCS Special Issue

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This issue features selected papers from the International Conference on Information Integration and Web-based Applications & Services (iiWAS2008) held in Linz, Austria, in November 24-26, 2008. iiWAS2008 marked the 10th anniversary of the iiWAS conference series. A number of important achievements marked the tenth anniversary of iiWAS, including being endorsed by the ACM SIGWEB and the proceedings is published by the ACM press making it available in the ACM Digital Library.

This year J.UCS and iiWAS conference series start the collaboration and it is also expected that this year iiWAS (iiWAS2009 to be held in December 2009 in Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia) will have its best papers appear in a special issue in J.UCS in 2010. Further details about iiWAS2009 can be found in the following website: <http://www.iivas.org/conferences/iivas2009/>.

Four papers are included in this issue. These papers have been extended from their original versions presented at the conference. The first two papers focus on XML database management, while the other two deal with hypermedia and web applications.

As general co-chairs and program co-chairs of iiWAS2008, as well as the guest editors of J.UCS special issue of iiWAS2008, we would like to congratulate the authors of papers appeared in this issue for their achievements in iiWAS2008 and their inclusion in this issue of J.UCS. We would also like to thank the PC members of

iiWAS2008 who conducted the initial reviewing process for the conference and the iiWAS2008 award co-chairs for selecting the best papers.

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Guest editors
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